

Determination of Differences in Chemical Compositions Between Heartwood and Sapwood of *Pinus pinea* and *Robinia pseudoacacia*

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Abstract

In this study, the chemical properties of heartwood and sapwood of *Pinus pinea* and *Robinia pseudoacacia* commonly grown in Turkey were investigated. Differences in the chemical compositions between heartwood and sapwood of *Pinus pinea* and *Robinia pseudoacacia* were analyzed accordance with relevant standards. It has been determined that the *Robinia pseudoacacia* sapwood has the highest holocellulose content as 80.71%, while *Pinus pinea* sapwood has the lowest holocellulose content as 72.24%. The cellulose contents of *Pinus pinea* sapwood and heartwood were found as 48.70% and 45.80%, respectively. The respective values for *Robinia pseudoacacia* were 49.31% and 50.53%. Besides, the lignin content of *Robinia pseudoacacia* was lower than that of *Pinus pinea*. According to obtained results, the chemical components of sapwood and heartwood of both species were different from each other. These chemical components have significantly effects on the physical and mechanical properties of wood-based products manufactured with these species. These properties are based on the lignin content. Besides, holocellulose, lignin, and cellulose contents are important for pulp and paper production in terms of pulp yield. It is desirable that the raw material to be used in the pulp and paper production has high holocellulose content and low lignin content. Consequently, *Robinia pseudoacacia* sapwood and *Pinus pinea* heartwood are more suitable for pulp and wood-based products production, respectively.

Keywords: Robinia pseudoacacia, Pinus pinea, chemical components, heartwood, sapwood.

Fıstıkçamı ve Yalancı Akasya Öz-Diri Odunlarının Kimyasal Bileşenleri Arasındaki Farklılıkların Belirlenmesi

Özet

Bu çalışmada, Türkiye’de yaygın bir şekilde yetişen Yalancı Akasya ve Fıstık Çamının öz ve diri odunlarının kimyasal bileşenleri arasındaki farklılıklar araştırılmıştır. Kimyasal bileşenler ilgili standartlara göre belirlenmiş ve farklılıklar analiz edilmiştir. Yalancı Akasya diri odununun en yüksek holoselüloz içeriğine (%80.71), fıstık çamı diri odunun ise en düşük holoselüloz içeriğine (%72.24) sahip olduğu belirlenmiştir. Fıstık Çamı diri ve öz odununun selüloz içeriği sırasıyla %48.70 ve %45.80 olarak bulunmuştur. Aynı değerler Yalancı Akasyada sırasıyla %49.31 ve %50.53 olarak tespit edilmiştir. Bunun yanında, lignin içeriği Yalancı Akasyada Fıstık Çamına göre daha düşük bulunmuştur. Elde edilen sonuçlara göre, her iki tür için de öz ve diri odunun kimyasal bileşenlerinde farklılıklar vardır. Bu farklılıklar oduna dayalı ürünlerin fiziksel ve mekaniksel özelliklerini etkilemektedir. Bu özelliklerde oluşacak farklılıklar genel olarak lignin içeriğinden kaynaklanmaktadır. Aynı zamanda, holoselüloz, lignin ve selüloz içeriği verim açısından kağıt ve kağıt hamuru üretimi için önemli bir parametredir. Kağıt hamuru ve kağıt üretiminde yüksek holoselüloz düşük lignin içeriği arzu edilmektedir. Sonuç olarak, Yalancı Akasya diri odunu oduna dayalı ürünlerin üretimine, Fıstık çamı öz odunu ise kağıt ve kağıt hamuru üretimine daha uygundur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yalancı Akasya, Fıstık Çamı, Kimyasal Bileşenler, Öz Odun, Diri Odun

INTRODUCTION

The investigation of chemical composition of wood is proper beneficial for pulp and paper production. Wood is a natural polymeric material that extremely variable in structure and in chemical composition as well. Even two trees of same species can have somewhat different percentage of the principal constituents in single samples of each, depending on the sources of the sampling in each tree. The chemical composition of wood varies with sapwood and heartwood. The chemical compositions of wood mainly contain cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and extractives (Roshani and Narendra, 2012).

The organic materials found in the heartwood are highly variable and complex. The origin of the extractives in the heartwood could not be adequately explained. The characteristic colors of normal heartwood are yellowish, orange, red, brownish tones resulting from the storage of extractives. In some cases, the color of the heartwood enhances the value of timber (eg. cherry, walnut, oak) (Atac, 2009). The presence of extractive substances in the heartwood reduces the permeability by inducing tyloses formation or causes pit aspiration. This makes it difficult to penetrate cooking liquor in the pulp production process and also to impregnate and dry. The heartwood is more resistant to fungi and insects than the sapwood. Decreased permeability prevents the growth of fungi because it restricts the intake of air and water in the wood. However, the main cause is the extractives which have poisonous effects on fungi and insects. Wood durability depends on the amount of extractive substances and toxicity (Panshin and De Zeeuw, 1980). Sapwood, also called alburnum, outer, living layers of the secondary wood of trees, which engage in transport of water and minerals to the crown of the tree. The cells therefore contain more water and lack the deposits of darkly staining chemical substances commonly found in heartwood. Sapwood is thus paler and softer than heartwood and can usually be distinguished in cross sections, as in tree stumps, although the proportions and distinctness of the two types are variable in different species (Vertessy et al., 1995).

Pinus pinea has a broad, somewhat flattened round canopy, and the tree will ultimately reach 25 to 30 meter in height though it is more often seen at 10 to 15 meter tall and wide (Fig. 1). The bright green, stiff, six-cm-long needles are arranged in slightly twisted bundles, and are joined by the heavy, five to six-inch-long cones which remain tightly closed on the tree for three years. The trunk is showy with narrow, foot-long orange plates set off nicely by darker fissures. *Robinia pseudoacacia* reaches a typical height of 12–30 m with a diameter of 0.61–1.22 m. Exceptionally, it may grow up to 52 meters tall and 1.6 meters diameter in very old trees. It is a very upright tree with a straight trunk and narrow crown which grows scraggly with age. The dark blue-green compound leaves with a contrasting lighter underside give this tree a beautiful appearance in the wind and contribute to its grace (Ozdemir et al., 2015).

The chemical components of the raw material to be used in wood products especially pulp and paper production have an important role. In this study, it was aimed to determine the chemical compositions of the heartwood and sapwood of *Pinus pinea* and *Robinia pseudoacacia* commonly grown in Turkey and differences between them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

P. pinea woods were obtained from İzmir Regional Directorate of Forestry, The Bergama Forestry Conservation Commission, Kozak Region. *R. pseudoacacia* woods were provided from the south side of the Ahir Mountain. Trees have been selected by observing to minimize wood defects such as knots, injuries, urine, insects, and fungi in the trunk. Selected examples are explained in detail in Table 1. Three pieces of 5 cm wheels were taken from the center of the body, 15 cm above the root, and 15 cm below the top.

Table 10. Informations about the trees used in the study

	Direction	Altitude (m)	Trunk Length (m)	Trunk Diameter (cm)	Age
<i>P. pinea</i>	South	550	6.10	35	31
<i>P. pinea</i>	North	627	6.12	30	28
<i>P. pinea</i>	East	605	6.50	31	29
<i>P. pinea</i>	West	620	5.00	27	25
<i>R. pseudoacacia</i>	South	1600	6.75	20	21

Wood samples were prepared according to TAPPI T 264 cm-07 for chemical analysis. *P. pinea* and *R. pseudoacacia* woods were analyzed for moisture, lignin, α -cellulose, ash, ethanol-toluene-acetone solubility, cold and hot water solubility and 1% NaOH solubility in accordance with the applicable standards: TAPPI T 264 om-88, TAPPI T 222 om-88, TAPPI T 203 os-71, TAPPI T 211 om-85, ASTM D1107 - 96, TAPPI T 207 om-88, TAPPI T 207 om-88, respectively. Holocellulose and cellulose contents of samples were determined according to Wise's chloride method (Wise and Karl, 1962) and Kurscher-Hoffer method (Browning, 1967), respectively. The raw material samples, 5 gr of oven-dried weight, were placed into a 500-mL Erlenmeyer flask, to which 200 mL of deionized water (having a temperature of 90 °C) was then added, followed by 10 mL of acetic acid and 2.5 g of 80% (w/w) NaClO₂. An optional 25-mL Erlenmeyer flask was inverted in the neck of the reaction flask. The flask was kept in a water bath 90 °C for 60 min, at which time 10 mL of acetic acid and 2.5 g of 80% (w/w) NaClO₂ were added with shaking. The 60-min cycle was repeated for up to 6 cycles. At the end, the flask was stoppered and cooled with cold water to stop the reaction. The reaction mixture was then filtered using a tared fritted disk glass thimble, washed with cold water and acetone, and dried at 103±2 °C until the crucible weight was constant, and the holocellulose content was calculated. The cellulose was obtained by refluxing wood meal three times for 1 h with a 1:4 (v/v) mixture of nitric acid and ethanol. Three replicates were done for each experiment, and mean values were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the chemical compositions and some solubility values of *P. pinea* and *R. pseudoacacia* wood. Holocellulose is the total polysaccharide fraction of wood or straw and the like that is made up of cellulose and all of the hemicelluloses and that is obtained by removing the extractives and the lignin from the original natural material. For this reason, it is important parameters for wood products industry. According to Table 2, the highest and lowest holocellulose contents were found in *R. pseudoacacia* sapwood (80.7%) and *P. pinea* sapwood (72.2%). In a study, the holocellulose contents of *P. nigra* and *A. nordmanniana* heartwoods were found as 64.42% and 70.02%, respectively. The respective values for the sapwoods were 67.46% and 70.78% (Atac, 2009). In another studies, the holocellulose contents of *Q. robur*, *F. orientalis*, *S. alba*, and eucalyptus were 70-74% (Atac, 2009), 77-80%, 78-80% (Eroglu and Usta, 1989), and 70-75% (Hus et al., 1975). The holocellulose findings of *P. pinea* and *R. pseudoacacia* were almost at the same level as the results of the literature in the related woods. Gonultas (2008) and Kirci (1986) were reported that the holocellulose contents of *P. pinea* and *R. pseudoacacia* were found as 72.88% and 81.50%, respectively.

Table 11. Chemical compositions of *P. pinea* and *R. pseudoacacia* heartwood and sapwood samples and other raw materials

Raw Materials	Holocellulose (%)	Cellulose (%)	Lignin (%)	Ash Content (%)	Solubilities				References
					Extractives (%)	1 % NaOH	Hot Water (%)	Cold Water (%)	
<i>P. pinea</i> heartwood	75.8	45.8	28.8	0.18	2.5	37.8	1.4	1.0	This study
<i>P. pinea</i> sapwood	72.2	48.7	27.5	0.36	2.3	32.5	1.1	0.9	This study
<i>R. pseudoacacia</i> heartwood	78.5	50.5	24.6	0.21	1.2	22.7	1.2	1.0	This study
<i>R. pseudoacacia</i> sapwood	80.7	49.3	23.9	0.41	0.9	20.3	1.1	1.0	This study
Softwood	63-74	40-45	25-32	0.2-0.5	1-5.8	8-10	1-5	0.5-4	Kirci, 2006
Hardwood	72-82	40-50	18-26	0.2-0.7	1-6.2	12-25	1-8	0.2-4	Kirci, 2006

Cellulose is one of many polymers found in nature. Wood, paper, and cotton all contain cellulose. It is indispensable for the pulp and paper industry. The cellulose content of hardwoods and softwoods is approximately 45-50%. In this study, the respective values for *P. pinea* and *R. pseudoacacia* were found as 45-48% and 49-50%, respectively. These values are at the highest level in the literature. In the paper industry, the yield is directly proportional to the cellulose content. Lignin is

an organic substance binding the cells, fibers and vessels which constitute wood and the lignified elements of plants, as in straw. After cellulose, it is the most abundant renewable carbon source on Earth. Lignin is not desired in the paper industry, although it is a desirable substance in some industries. In this study, the lignin contents of *P. pinea* and *R. pseudoacacia* heartwood and sapwood were in accordance with the literature. Chemical composition is a relevant wood quality parameter and decisive for pulping suitability (Pereira et al., 2003). Cellulose and lignin are important for interpreting the pulping behavior as well as for determining the pulp quality (Valente et al., 1992).

The high NaOH (1%) solubility is due to the presence of low molecular weight carbohydrates and other alkali-soluble matters (Tutus and Eroglu, 2003). Also, NaOH solubility indicates the extent of fiber degradation during pulping process (Zawawi et al., 2014). Cold water solubility provides a measure of tannins, sugars, gums, and coloring matter. Hot water solubility removes, in addition, starches (ASTM, 2013). In this study, NaOH (1%) solubility was found higher than literature. The extractives and water solubilities of *P. pinea* and *R. pseudoacacia* heartwood and sapwood were consistent with previous studies.

When the species' heartwood and sapwood compare to each other, *R. pseudoacacia* sapwood has the highest holocellulose content than heartwood. But the cellulose content of sapwood was lower than heartwood. This is due to the hemicellulose content. As mentioned above, holocellulose consists of cellulose and hemicellulose. The heartwood of *P. pinea* has higher holocellulose content than the sapwood. The lignin contents of both species' heartwoods were found to be higher than those of sapwoods. Besides, the amount of extractive matter of heartwoods was higher than that of sapwood.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the chemical properties of *P. pinea* and *R. pseudoacacia* heartwood and sapwood were determined, and these results were compared with each other and previous studies. The following conclusions were obtained from this study:

1. In comparison between heartwood and sapwood, the lignin content of sapwood was higher than that of heartwood. Besides, *P. pinea*'s lignin content was higher in both heartwood and sapwood than *R. pseudoacacia*.
2. High ash content was observed mostly in the sapwood. *R. pseudoacacia* heartwood gave the highest ash content when compared with *P. pinea*.
3. The cellulose and holocellulose contents of the *P. pinea* heartwood were found to be higher than sapwood, but *R. pseudoacacia* sapwood were higher than heartwood.

Due to the high levels of holocellulose and cellulose content, *R. pseudoacacia* sapwood should be considered to be utilized in pulp and paper industries. Since *P. pinea* contains high lignin content, it can be evaluated in carbon industries.

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